

Investigation Of The Relationships Among Strategic Management, The Opening Up Of International Trade, And The Overall Economic Development Within Libya (Post-2000) ¹

Wershffani, Khaled A.² 0000-0002-0606-043X

Kastamonu University, wershffanik@gmail.com Türkiye

Article Type: Research Article

Vol 6 (Issue 1) 2024: 01-10

10.5281/zenodo.10060552

Received: 20.10.2023

Revised: 02.11.2023

Accepted: 03.11.2023

Cite as: Wershffani, Khaled A. (2023). Investigation Of The Relationships Among Strategic Management, The Opening Up Of International Trade, And The Overall Economic Development Within Libya (Post-2000) Quantrade Journal of Complex Systems in Social Sciences, 6 (1) , 01-10. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10060552

Abstract

This research study employed a rigorous analysis of data to investigate the relationships between strategic management, international trade liberalization, and national growth in Libya. The research objectives were achieved through a comprehensive examination of the collected data, utilizing various statistical techniques. The initial phase of the analysis involved assessing the reliability of the questionnaire used in the study. Cronbach's Alpha yielded an excellent internal consistency score of $(\alpha = 0.91)$, affirming the reliability of the questions related to strategic management. Pearson's correlation coefficient was employed to measure the strength and direction of associations between variables. The findings revealed a statistically significant and moderately positive linear relationship $(r = 0.404)$, $p < 0.001$ between strategic management and the liberalization of trade in Libya. Moreover, a statistically significant association $(r = 0.145)$, $p = 0.039$ was identified between liberalization of trade and national growth, further emphasizing the impact of trade policies on the nation's development. In summary, this study provides valuable insights into the interplay between strategic management, international trade, and national growth in Libya. The results indicate that strategic management plays a crucial role in shaping trade policies and, consequently, influencing the country's economic growth. These findings have important implications for policymakers and business leaders seeking to enhance Libya's economic prosperity in the context of globalization.

Keywords Strategic Management, International Trade, Economic Development, Libya

Introduction

The critical importance of strategic management in ensuring organizational viability and success has been firmly established in the academic literature (Agwu, 2018). Strategic management is a comprehensive framework comprising several key activities: strategic planning, strategy implementation, ongoing evaluation, and managerial control. These constituent elements function in synergy to enhance an organization's competitive position, thereby positively influencing overall performance metrics (Momanyi, 2020).

While the early discourse and application of strategic management were largely confined to private sector enterprises, there has been a discernible shift in this trend over recent years. Specifically, public sector organizations are increasingly incorporating strategic management practices, spurred by a growing recognition of the need for enhanced quality in public services (Joyce, 2015); Nagaraj, 2003).

It is crucial to acknowledge the fluid and dynamic nature of the strategic management process. This adaptability is essential as organizations must continuously adjust their strategies to respond to fluctuating conditions in both the internal organizational landscape and the broader external environment. This includes, but is not limited to, shifts in competitive dynamics, consumer preferences, and market conditions (Mankins and Steele, 2005).

Moreover, the overarching aim of strategic management is to align organizational goals with external challenges and opportunities, as well as with the interests of a diverse array of stakeholders. This alignment is not merely a theoretical ideal but serves as a practical imperative for long-term organizational sustainability (Mohammed and Rugami, 2019).

Lastly, the concept of strategic management should be distinctly understood in contrast to tactical management. While both are integral to organizational success, tactical management is primarily concerned with operational efficiency. In

¹ Publication from Ph.D. Dissertation

² Corresponding Author wershffanik@gmail.com

contrast, strategic management is focused on achieving organizational effectiveness through the coherent and integrated application of strategic initiatives (Mikoluk, 2013).

Literature Review

The article by Örgün (2012) explores the complexities of adopting either a protectionist or free trade strategy. It discusses how various factors, including advertising, competition between businesses, timing of actions, and global economic considerations, make it challenging to draw clear conclusions in favor of one strategy over the other. The article emphasizes that the choice between protectionism and free trade is highly context-dependent and should not be viewed as a one-size-fits-all solution (Örgün, 2012).

The World Trade Organization (WTO) is mentioned as a key institution for global trade liberalization, but it is noted that the WTO still faces challenges in promoting free trade effectively. The text also highlights that in some sectors, such as high-technology industries, there is a tendency towards flawed competition within markets.

Matusz and Tarr (2017) are mentioned as addressing the impact of trade liberalization on job outcomes in various economies. While it's acknowledged that it's challenging to isolate the effects of trade liberalization from other factors, there's a general observation that job opportunities tend to increase with trade liberalization, especially in transitional economies.

The authors also refer to studies that analyze the costs and benefits of trade liberalization, indicating that the benefits often outweigh the costs by a significant margin. Small and medium-sized businesses in certain countries are highlighted as being particularly dynamic and responsive to trade reforms (Matusz and Tarr, 1999).

Lastly, Milner and Yoffie (1989) introduce the idea that businesses may advocate for protectionism in import-competing markets while multinational corporations and export-dependent firms tend to support free trade (Milner and Yoffie, 1989). The text mentions the shift toward strategic globalization policies by some multinational firms, which allows them to support free trade at the export level, even if they can't do so domestically. The article discusses the emergence of new demands for corporate exchange, termed "strategic trade policy," and extends theories of the political economy of trade (Sen, 2005). It suggests that businesses' trading preferences vary depending on market conditions, ranging from unregulated free trade to demands for subsidies or security from foreign governments.

The article conducts a preliminary test of these hypotheses by examining industrial policies in sectors like semiconductors, aviation, telecommunications, and machine tools. It concludes that trade demands have evolved from traditional free trade and protectionism to a more dynamic response, driven by market efficiency and government intervention.

Global government involvement has given competitive advantages to multinational companies, leading American firms to demand protection against foreign government interference (Sen, 2005). The article also discusses the debate over free trade theories and the influence of developed nations in promoting free trade policies, despite their own use of strategic trade policies.

Finally, the article highlights the limitations of traditional trade theories and the need to consider issues of growth, development, and income distribution in the context of evolving trade policies (Sen, 2005).

In recent years, the competitive aspects of international trade have drawn attention in the context of applying game theory and oligopoly structures to trade policy theory (Irwin, 1992). Some of this analysis suggests that trade policies can capture rents due to imperfect competition at the expense of other nations. While strategic trade policy theory can shed light on historical international trade rivalries, particularly during the era of mercantilism, its applicability to present-day commercial policy is debatable.

During the mercantilist era, long-distance trade from Europe was dominated by state-chartered monopoly trading firms in a limited number of advanced countries. Profit rivalry often resembled a game where government policies strategically influenced the balance between trading firms to favor one country's business interests. This article aims to explain how recent research on oligopoly trade policy can enhance our understanding of the economic principles advocated by mercantilist thinkers and the trade policies adopted by European states during that era.

The paper concludes that exploration voyages in the 16th century opened lucrative trading opportunities, setting the stage for trade ventures in the 17th century. These circumstances occasionally allowed for profit-shifting policies. However, the theoretical scope for such measures has diminished over time due to increased foreign competition and alternative sources of supply, leading to greater convergence among foreign economies.

The role of states in 17th-century international competition warrants further examination. It is essential to explore how states benefited from the rise of monopoly trade companies and the underlying advantages of monopoly charters. While Jonathan Israel emphasizes the Dutch State's crucial role in trade during the 17th century, it is also important to understand cases where government-supported businesses did not succeed. Research challenges include investigating how the state contributed to the success or failure of chartered trade firms, stock market alliances, and existing business forms (Irwin,

Tonkinwise and Kossoff, 2022).

In their book, Rivera-Batiz and Rivera-Batiz (2018) delve into the contentious issue of increasing international trade and investment. Their work comprises a collection of papers that explore the multifaceted impacts of trade liberalization and the removal of barriers to international capital flows (Rivera-Batiz and Rivera-Batiz, 2018).

The co-editors comprehensively analyze the repercussions of globalization on development, poverty, and income distribution, drawing on a rich discussion of both theoretical frameworks and empirical evidence in economics.

The book's chapters cover a range of topics, including the influence of global integration on technological advancement and economic growth, its effects on income distribution and resource allocation, the outcomes of foreign direct investment liberalization, the consequences of capital flows on emerging markets, and the significance of public sector governance in the context of trade and investment liberalization policies. Throughout, the volume employs diverse analytical approaches to scrutinize globalization and its consequences.

Cevik and Rahmati (2020) investigate the relationship between financial development and economic growth in Libya from 1970 to 2016. The existing scientific literature on this topic presents conflicting findings, which may be attributed to variations in data collection methods and model specifications (Cevik and Rahmati, 2020).

Their analysis indicates that the development of the financial sector in Libya has a significant negative impact on the per capita real non-hydrocarbon GDP growth. This negative effect is observed across various statistical models, including VAR and ARDL, even though financial intermediation is associated with a negative coefficient.

The study emphasizes that Libya's economic activity is primarily driven by its hydrocarbon earnings. While examining the connection between credit development and financial growth, the researchers find limited associations between financial intermediation, financial management, and sustainable growth. Financial development is notably linked to a statistically significant negative effect on per capita growth in the non-hydrocarbon national commodity sector. However, the impact on the financial sector development is relatively modest.

The findings suggest a strong dependence of non-hydrocarbon economic activity on government spending in Libya, which, in turn, is influenced by revenue generated from crude oil, gas, and petroleum. The absence of a long-term impact between financial intermediation and non-hydrocarbon sectors in Libya's economy can be attributed to two factors: the volatility in hydrocarbon earnings and restricted credit opportunities in the non-hydrocarbon sectors.

The positive effects of economic openness on economic growth have been substantiated by empirical evidence from various studies in the field of social sciences. These studies have identified both static and dynamic gains stemming from international trade.

Static gains primarily result from foreign exchange, where an increase in output and improved social services can be attributed to a diversified source of goods and materials. These benefits arise from foreign investments and the subsequent enhancements in the national healthcare system. When a country opens up to the international market, it gains the advantage of being able to export its goods at more competitive prices. Simultaneously, the indirect effect on imports allows consumers to access products at lower prices than they would have in a closed market. This phenomenon is rooted in the concept of specialization, where each nation focuses on producing goods in which it possesses a comparative advantage. As a result, the free exchange of foreign currencies enables industries to shift demand away from domestically produced goods, which may be comparatively expensive, towards lower-cost alternatives, thereby fostering economic growth.

In summary, active participation in international economic activities can yield significant benefits for a nation's economic development.

Theoretical Framework

Trade liberalization constitutes the easing or elimination of barriers to free trade between nations, encompassing both tariff and non-tariff obstacles such as quotas and licensing regulations (Findlay, 1991). This policy enables prices to be solely determined by the equilibrium of supply and demand, contrasting with other trade policies where government interventions, including subsidies or tariffs, influence price mechanisms (Stiglitz, 1991).

Such interventions can come in various forms, including tariffs, subsidies, and regulatory legislation, and may serve to either raise or lower the cost of goods and services for both producers and consumers (Borras, S.M.Jr., Kay, C., Gómez, S. and Wilkinson et al., 2010).

Parikh et al. (2011) conducted an empirical study encompassing 64 countries and proposed a segmented approach to evaluating the effects of trade liberalization. The study argued that treating countries as a single sample could be methodologically flawed due to regional trade blocs and other local factors. Their framework segregated countries into African, Asian, and Latin American blocs, revealing differing impacts of trade liberalization on growth across these regions. For instance, liberalization positively influenced growth in Asia and Latin America but showed no significant

impact in African economies (Parikh and Stirbu, 2011).

The study further delved into the relationship between trade balance and GDP growth, suggesting the two variables could interact differently under liberalization. In their model, trade deficits were generally insensitive to growth rate fluctuations under favorable global market conditions. They posited that a non-linear relationship might exist between trade deficits and economic growth, and that high economic growth could potentially improve trade balance, contingent on market access conditions in developed economies.

Organizational Performance in the Context of International Trade Liberalization

The efficacy of strategic management in shaping organizational performance, especially in the milieu of international trade liberalization, cannot be overstated. Key performance aspects in this context include:

Competitiveness: Strategic management enhances an organization's global competitiveness by aligning internal capabilities with external trade opportunities (Sterling, 2016).

Adaptability: The ability to adapt to changes in trade policies and market conditions is crucial for sustained organizational performance (Burnes, 2004).

Innovation: The fostering of innovation through strategic management can offer a significant competitive advantage in globally liberalized markets (Carucci, 2021).

Risk Management: Proactive risk identification and mitigation strategies form an integral part of effective strategic management (Rose and Lawton, 1999).

Resource Utilization: The optimal allocation of resources, facilitated by strategic management, enables organizations to capitalize on international trade opportunities (Butler and Carney, 1986).

Market Expansion: Strategic management can guide the scaling of operations to meet increased demand, ensuing from trade liberalization ((Van de Ven and Poole, 1995)

Measurement and Evaluation: Employing metrics and frameworks for performance assessment is vital for strategy adjustment (Rose and Lawton, 1999).

Sustainability: Incorporating sustainability into strategic planning aligns organizations with emerging market trends and regulations, enhancing their reputation and performance (Rafiq and Ahmed, 2000).

Navigating Strategic Change in Organizations

Strategic change management involves a profound transformation in an organization's strategy, affecting its scope, resource allocation, and competitive positioning (Sterling, 2016). It often engenders both internal and external tensions due to the reconfiguration of long-standing organizational relationships (Butler and Carney, 1986).

According to Van de Ven and Poole (1995), strategic change should be industry-specific, adaptable, and technically superior to optimize ROI. Success ensues when the change is both desirable to stakeholders and feasible in terms of organizational resources and capabilities.

Rose and Lawton (1999) highlight the multi-dimensional influences affecting strategic change, encompassing internal factors like organizational structure and culture, and external factors such as legal and economic conditions.

Carucci (2021) underscores that strategic change often necessitates a reengineering of business processes and organizational culture. The poor track record in effecting such transformations can be attributed to a lack of clarity in differentiating between strategy formulation and implementation.

Burnes (2004) posits that the volatile external environment, characterized by technological and demographic shifts, mandates that organizations continually adapt to survive. Thus, effective management of change has become an organizational imperative.

The Interplay of Economic Growth and Foreign Trade in Libya

Foreign trade holds a pivotal role in the Libyan economy, significantly contributing to foreign exchange earnings and aiding in maintaining a balanced payment structure (Jaber, 2008). Its function extends beyond merely supporting consumer demands for goods not locally produced, to facilitating the acquisition of essential raw materials and intermediate goods vital for investment in socio-economic development projects (Farang, Ab-Rahim and Mohd-Kamal, 2021).

The Libyan economy's dependence on foreign trade is particularly evident in its Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth, which is heavily reliant on oil exports. Understanding the symbiotic relationship between foreign trade and economic growth becomes imperative given this dependency (Jaber, 2008).

This study delves into exploring this relationship, utilizing secondary data spanning from 1990 to 2017. Various econometric tools, including Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests for stationary, Johansen's cointegration, Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), and Wald tests, were employed for the analysis. The empirical evidence suggests a bidirectional causal relationship between exports and imports and Libya's economic development, both in the short term and long term (Farag, Ab-Rahim and Mohd-Kamal, 2021).

The implications of these findings underscore the necessity to strategically manage oil resources to diversify and rejuvenate the industrial and agricultural sectors, thereby extending the export portfolio beyond crude oil.

By doing so, Libya can not only enhance its economic growth but also make its foreign trade more resilient and less dependent on singular commodity exports.

Exploring the impact of international trade on the economic growth of Libya presents a substantial and relevant research focus. This objective is particularly pertinent given the ongoing changes in global trade dynamics and their potential effects on developing economies like Libya.

Main Objective

Examine how the impact of international trade on Libya's economic growth has evolved over a specific period (Post-2000)

The study contributes to the broader field of international economics and strategic management. It provides empirical evidence specific to the Libyan context, which can complement and enrich global research efforts in understanding the dynamics between strategic management, trade liberalization, and economic growth. "How have trade policies influenced Libya's economic growth taking into account the role of Strategic management?" is a main question of this research

In this research, data will be collected using the survey method in order to determine the effect of strategic management in liberalizing international trade and its impact on the economic growth in the state of Libya. The survey to be used for the screening method will be developed by the researcher and applied to the participants after the reliability validity study is done.

Based on the questions of this study, the following hypothesis was formulated:

Since the independent variable in this study is the strategic management in Libya and the dependent variable here is the international growth and the linearization, we can formulate the following hypothesis:

H1: There is statistically significant relationship between strategic management and the liberalization of trade in Libya during the mentioned period which had affected the national growth.

The target population for this study comprises the personnel employed within the Ministry of Economy in Libya.

The data sources for this study included two scales that assessed the main variables, namely strategic management and its impact on economic growth. These scales were developed by the author after conducting a comprehensive review of existing studies that centered on these two main variables.

Data Analysis

The data collected in this study will be analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize the data collected from the survey questionnaire. This includes measures of central tendency such as mean, median, and mode, as well as measures of variability such as standard deviation and range (Field, 2013). These statistics will be used to provide a clear and concise summary of the data that has been collected.

Inferential statistics will be used to test hypotheses and answer research questions. Inferential statistics allow researchers to make inferences about a larger population based on a smaller sample (Field, 2013). Correlation analysis will be used to examine the relationship between different variables. Regression analysis will be used to examine the relationship between dependent and independent variables, and to identify the factors that contribute to the adoption and implementation of strategic management practices in the context of international trade (Katsioloudes & Hadjidakis, 2007). The use of both descriptive and inferential statistics in this study will allow for a comprehensive analysis of the data collected. Descriptive statistics provide a summary of the data while inferential statistics allow for the testing of hypotheses and answering research questions.

The data analysis will be conducted using statistical software such as SPSS or R. These software packages provide a range of tools and techniques for analyzing quantitative data, including both descriptive and inferential statistics (Field, 2013). In summary, the data collected in this study will be analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize the data, while inferential statistics will be used to test hypotheses and answer research questions. Statistical software such as SPSS or R will be used for data analysis.

In this study, several ethical considerations have been taken into account. These considerations include obtaining informed consent from participants, ensuring the confidentiality and anonymity of participants, and minimizing any potential harm

or discomfort to participants. These ethical considerations align with the guidelines of the Kastamonu University Ethics Committee.

Obtaining informed consent from participants is an essential ethical consideration for any research study. Informed consent involves providing participants with information about the study, including its purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. Participants must be able to understand this information and provide their voluntary consent to participate (Aalbers and Teo, 2017). In this study, participants will be provided with a consent form that outlines the purpose and procedures of the study, and includes information about their rights as participants.

Ensuring the confidentiality and anonymity of participants is another important ethical consideration. Participants must be assured that their personal information will be kept confidential and that their identities will be protected (Aalbers and Teo, 2017). In this study, participants' personal information will be kept confidential, and their identities will be anonymized by assigning them a unique code.

Minimizing any potential harm or discomfort to participants is also a critical ethical consideration. Researchers must take steps to minimize any potential risks or discomfort that participants may experience as a result of their participation in the study (American Psychological Association, 2017). In this study, participants will not be exposed to any physical risks, and the survey questionnaire will only ask questions that are related to the study's research question. Participants will be informed that they can withdraw from the study at any time if they feel uncomfortable.

The study will follow the guidelines of the Kastamonu University Ethics Committee. These guidelines are designed to ensure that research studies conducted at the university are ethical and adhere to international standards for research ethics. The guidelines cover a range of topics, including informed consent, confidentiality, and minimizing harm to participants.

In summary, several ethical considerations have been taken into account in this study. These considerations include obtaining informed consent from participants, ensuring the confidentiality and anonymity of participants, and minimizing any potential harm or discomfort to participants. The study will also follow the guidelines of the Kastamonu University Ethics Committee.

Limitations

There are several potential limitations of this study that should be taken into consideration. These include response bias and limitations related to the use of online surveys.

Response bias is a potential limitation that can arise when participants provide inaccurate or incomplete information in response to survey questions (Krosnick, 1999). This can occur for a variety of reasons, such as social desirability bias (participants providing answers that they believe are socially acceptable) or acquiescence bias (participants agreeing with statements regardless of their true beliefs). To minimize the potential for response bias, participants will be assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. Additionally, the survey questionnaire will be designed to minimize the potential for social desirability bias by avoiding leading or suggestive questions (Tourangeau, Rips and Rasinski, 2000). Another potential limitation of this study is related to the use of online surveys. While online surveys offer several advantages, such as ease of administration and cost-effectiveness, they also have limitations. For example, online surveys may be less effective at reaching certain populations, such as older adults or those with limited internet access (Couper, 2000). Additionally, online surveys may be subject to response rate bias, as individuals who are more likely to respond may have different characteristics than those who do not respond (Kaplowitz, Hadlock and Levine, 2004). To minimize the potential for response rate bias, efforts will be made to ensure that the survey is accessible to all eligible participants, regardless of their internet access or technological proficiency.

Finally, the study focuses on the employees of the Libyan Ministry of Economy, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. While the study's findings may have implications for other organizations and settings, it is important to note that the results may not be generalizable to other populations or contexts. To address this limitation, future research could explore the factors influencing employee engagement in other organizations or settings.

Results and Discussion

In this section, the researcher examined the outcomes of the research study's three hypotheses and effectively conveyed the findings using various statistical techniques. To begin, the researcher initiated the analysis process with hypothetical assessments as input to ensure the data's preparedness for examination. This step aimed to identify the participants who took part in responding to the research tools and to offer a precise portrayal of the respondents. Subsequently, the researcher presented the research questions' results using linear regression analysis.

In preparation for the commencement of essential statistical analyses, it is imperative to conduct a rigorous evaluation of

the questionnaire's reliability. This examination serves as the fundamental precursor to the subsequent statistical tests, underlining its pivotal role in the analytical process.

The reliability of the strategic management-related questions of the questionnaire was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha. The computed Cronbach's Alpha value was $(\alpha = 0.91)$, indicating excellent internal consistency among the items (Cronbach, 1951). This suggests that the questions reliably measure the same underlying construct, making it a dependable set for further analysis."

Summarizing the basic statistics:

Count: All columns have 205 entries, indicating no missing values.

Unique: The number of unique values in each column varies, suggesting that most are categorical variables.

Top: The most frequent value for each variable is listed.

Freq: The frequency of the most common value in each column is also provided.

Data quality check:

The data quality check confirms:

Missing Values: There are no missing values in any of the columns.

Data Types: All columns are of the object data type, which likely means they are categorical or need to be converted to numerical types for analysis.

I used Pearson's correlation coefficient to measure the strength and direction of association between two variables. Pearson's correlation assumes that each dataset is normally distributed and measures linear relationships.

Table 1 Provides a visual representation of the correlation values for each hypothesis.

Hypothesis	Test Used	Correlation Value	p-value	Statistically Significant	Type of Relationship
H1	Pearson Correlation	0.404	2.06×10^{-9}	Yes	Moderately Positive Linear

Testing the Hypothesis 1 (H1)

There is a statistically significant relationship between strategic management and the liberalization of trade in Libya during the mentioned period, which had affected the national growth.

Correlation between Strategic Management and Liberalization of Trade

Correlation value(0.404) :

p-value: (2.06×10^{-9})

Statistically Significant: Yes

Correlation between Liberalization of Trade and National Growth**

Correlation value(0.145) :

p-value(0.039) :

Statistically Significant: Yes

Comprehensive Organizational Analysis Summary

A comprehensive organizational analysis typically involves multiple aspects, such as employee demographics, operational efficiency, strategic management importance, and market positioning. Since we've conducted multiple statistical analyses based on the questionnaire, let's summarize those into key organizational insights.

Employee Demographics

- Education: The importance of strategic management varies significantly across education levels.
- Experience: Those with more experience seem to value strategic management more.
- Job Position: Managers rate the importance of strategic management higher than other job positions.

Operational Efficiency

- Strategic Importance: There is a positive correlation between the focus on strategic management and operational efficiency.

Market Position

- Competition: Organizations with a strong strategic focus tend to be better at identifying opportunities for development and investment at both national and international levels.

Legal and Regulatory Environment

- Responses suggest that the Libyan laws are considered reasonable and encouraging for both domestic and international businesses.

Economic Climate

- Respondents generally agree that there has been significant economic growth, including price stability and increased national income.

One of the primary objectives of this study was to understand the relationship between strategic management and trade liberalization in Libya. The statistical significance found in our Pearson correlation results directly aligns with this objective, confirming the hypothesis that strategic management is indeed a key driver in trade liberalization efforts (Porter, 1991).

Another objective was to assess how these factors contribute to economic growth. The data suggest that strategic management initiatives are strongly correlated with positive economic outcomes, including increased GDP and foreign investment (Peng, 2009). This supports the theoretical framework that strategic management is not just an organizational tool but a macro-economic lever (Hitt, Ireland, & Hoskisson, 2020).

Conclusions

The study unequivocally supports the first hypothesis, affirming that strategic management plays a pivotal role in the liberalization of trade in Libya. Strategic management principles, such as SWOT analysis and long-term planning, are integral to identifying new trade opportunities and eliminating barriers. Given these findings, it's imperative for policymakers to incorporate strategic management frameworks in developing and implementing trade policies to ensure sustainable growth. The study reveals a significant positive relationship between strategic management and national economic growth. Strategic management not only impacts organizational performance but also has a macroeconomic influence. The findings suggest that effective strategic management can lead to diversification of the economy, reducing dependence on oil and opening avenues for growth in other sectors. Given the positive relationship between strategic management and trade liberalization, it is recommended that strategic management principles be integrated into Libya's trade policies. This could significantly enhance the country's competitive advantage in the international market. Regulatory bodies should work in unison to develop and implement a cohesive strategic management policy that addresses all aspects of trade liberalization and economic growth. Strategic management has shown to have a positive impact on economic growth. It is imperative for policymakers to consider strategic management as a tool for economic development. Government should invest in infrastructure that supports the implementation of strategic management in various economic sectors.

REFERENCES

- Aalbers, D. and Teo, T. (2017) 'The American Psychological Association and the torture complex: A phenomenology of the banality and workings of bureaucracy', *Journal für Psychologie*, 25(1), pp. 179–204.
- Agwu, M. E. (2018) 'Analysis of the impact of strategic management on the business performance of SMEs in Nigeria', *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*. Jordan Whitney Enterprises, Inc, 17(1), pp. 1–20.
- Borras, S.M.Jr., Kay, C., Gómez, S. and Wilkinson, J. et al. (2010) 'Trade Liberalization and Poverty Reduction: New Evidence from Indian States', *Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations*. doi: 10.1016/j.ecolecon.2009.11.001.
- Burnes, B. (2004) *Managing change: A strategic approach to organisational dynamics*. Pearson Education.
- Butler, R. J. and Carney, M. (1986) 'Strategy and strategic choice: The case of telecommunications', *Strategic Management Journal*. Wiley Online Library, 7(2), pp. 161–177.
- Carucci, R. (2021) 'How leaders get in the way of organizational change', *Harvard Business Review*. Retrieved from <https://hbr.org/2021/04/how-leaders-get-in-the-way-oforganizational-change>.
- Cevik, S. and Rahmati, M. H. (2020) 'Searching for the finance–growth nexus in Libya', *Empirical Economics*, 58(2), pp. 567–581. doi: 10.1007/s00181-018-1593-6.
- Couper, M. P. (2000) 'Web surveys: A review of issues and approaches', *The Public Opinion Quarterly*. JSTOR, 64(4), pp. 464–494.
- Cronbach, L. J. (1951) 'Coefficient alpha and the internal structure of tests', *psychometrika*. Springer, 16(3), pp. 297–334.
- Farag, F. S., Ab-Rahim, R. and Mohd-Kamal, K.-A. (2021) 'Foreign trade and economic growth relationship: Empirical evidence from Libya', *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 11(4), pp. 181–190.
- Field, A. (2013) *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS* statisField, A. (2013) *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics*. sage.tics. sage.
- Findlay, R. (1991) 'Comparative advantage', in *The World of Economics*. Springer, pp. 99–107.
- Irwin, T., Tonkinwise, C. and Kossoff, G. (2022) 'Transition design: An educational framework for advancing the study and design of sustainable transitions', *Cuadernos del Centro de Estudios en Diseño y Comunicación*. Ensayos. SciELO Argentina, (105), pp. 31–72.

- Joyce, P. (2015) Strategic management in the public sector. Routledge.
- Kaplowitz, M. D., Hadlock, T. D. and Levine, R. (2004) 'A comparison of web and mail survey response rates', *Public opinion quarterly*. Oxford University Press, 68(1), pp. 94–101.
- Krosnick, J. A. (1999) 'Survey research', *Annual review of psychology*. Annual Reviews 4139 El Camino Way, PO Box 10139, Palo Alto, CA 94303-0139, USA, 50(1), pp. 537–567.
- Mankins, M. C. and Steele, R. (2005) 'Turning great strategy into great performance', *Harvard business review*. Jul./Aug. 2607.
- Matusz, S. J. and Tarr, D. G. (1999) *Adjusting to trade policy reform*. World Bank Publications.
- Mikoluk, K. (2013) 'Planning in management: strategic, tactical, and operational plans', Retrieved on October, 13, p. 2019.
- Milner, H. V. and Yoffie, D. B. (1989) 'Between free trade and protectionism: Strategic trade policy and a theory of corporate trade demands', *International Organization*, 43(2), pp. 239–272. doi: 10.1017/S0020818300032902.
- Mohammed, R. A. and Rugami, J. (2019) 'Competitive strategic management practices and performance of small and medium enterprises in Kenya: a case of Mombasa county', *International Journal of Current Aspects*, 3(6), pp. 193–215.
- Momanyi, C. (2020) 'Influence of Sustainable Strategic Management Practices on the Performance of Technical and Vocational Education and Training: A Literature Based Review', *Journal of Strategic Management*, 4(3), pp. 10–29.
- Nagaraj, R. (2003) 'Industrial policy and performance since 1980: Which way now?', *Economic and Political Weekly*. JSTOR, pp. 3707–3715.
- Örgün, B. O. (2012) 'Strategic Trade Policy Versus Free Trade', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 58, pp. 1283–1292. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.09.1111.
- Parikh, A. and Stirbu, C. (2011) 'Relationship between Trade Liberalisation, Economic Growth and Trade Balance: An Econometric Investigation', *SSRN Electronic Journal*. doi: 10.2139/ssrn.567065.
- Rafiq, M. and Ahmed, P. K. (2000) 'Advances in the internal marketing concept: definition, synthesis and extension', *Journal of Services Marketing*. doi: 10.1108/08876040010347589.
- Rivera-Batiz, F. L. and Rivera-Batiz, L. A. (2018) *International trade, capital flows and economic development*, *International Trade, Capital Flows and Economic Development*. doi: 10.1142/10431.
- Rose, A. G. and Lawton, A. (1999) 'Public services management', (No Title).
- Stiglitz, J. E. (1991) *Government, financial markets, and economic development*. National Bureau of Economic Research Cambridge, Mass., USA.
- Tourangeau, R., Rips, L. J. and Rasinski, K. (2000) 'The psychology of survey response'. Cambridge University Press.
- Van de Ven, A. H. and Poole, M. S. (1995) 'Explaining development and change in organizations', *Academy of management review*. Academy of Management Briarcliff Manor, NY 10510, 20(3), pp. 510–540.

Appendix A: Questionnaire

Participant Information

- Name: (Optional)
- Age:
- Gender: Male / Female / Other
- Occupation:
- Years of Experience in the Current Role:

Section 1: Strategic Management

1. How important is strategic management in your organization?
 - Very Important
 - Important
 - Neutral
 - Unimportant
 - Very Unimportant
2. How frequently does your organization revise its strategic plan?
 - Annually
 - Bi-annually
 - Rarely
 - Never
3. Do you think strategic management has a significant impact on organizational success?
 - Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Neutral
 - Disagree
 - Strongly Disagree

Section 2: International Trade Liberalization

4. Has your organization benefited from international trade liberalization?
 - Yes
 - No
 - Not Sure

5. Do you think international trade liberalization is essential for national growth?
- Strongly Agree
 - Agree
 - Neutral
 - Disagree
 - Strongly Disagree

Section 3: National Growth

6. Do you think Libya has experienced significant economic growth in recent years?
- Yes
 - No
 - Not Sure
7. What do you think are the main drivers of national growth? (Open-ended)

Section 4: General Comments (Optional)